

European Research Council
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European Research Council (ERC)

SHANNON

Secure Hardware with AdvaNced NONvolatile memories

Data Management Plan

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

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Project Funding

Project Acronym	Project Number
SHANNON	101069299

Revision and History Chart

Version	Date	Author	Comment
1.0	22.03.2023	Lorenzo Cattaneo, Piergiulio Mannocci, Daniele Ielmini	Original version
1.1	27.04.2023	Lorenzo Cattaneo, Piergiulio Mannocci, Daniele Ielmini	Revised version
1.2			
1.3			
1.4			

Introduction

This document provides the plan for managing the data generated and collected during the project lifetime. The purpose of this data management plan (DMP) is to ensure that all generated and collected data related to the SHANNON project will follow the FAIR data management policy, ensuring findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data.

SHANNON is a project that will create research scientific data in the field of hardware security, emerging nonvolatile memory devices, machine learning, industrial algorithms, and component fabrication. The DMP covers:

i) the handling of research data during and after the project, ii) description of datasets that will be collected, processed, and/or generated, iii) what methodology and standards will be applied, iv) the level of accessibility/confidentiality of the data, and v) how data preservation will take place. The Data Management Plan is prepared based on the “ERC Data Management Plan Template”.

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

SUMMARY

[Dataset Information Template](#)

Most of the datasets will be generated from technical design, experimental measurements and physical modelling performed throughout the project lifetime. Descriptions of the datasets are categorized into both qualitative and quantitative aspects, as shown in the table reported below. There is a total of 6 datasets that are expected to be generated within SHANNON project, at the current stage. Additional dataset types or requirements may be added over the course of the project as they are identified and defined.

Dataset ref code	Reference code of the dataset
Dataset Name	Name of the dataset
Dataset Description	Description of the data type and source of the following
Purpose	To provide a full documentation of the simulation algorithms, methods of visualization and analysis, also in connection to the experimental observation
Type	Types of data could be report, paper, interview, expert or organization contact, details, images, video, audio, presentation, or note
Format	Data formats could be: XLSX, CSV (tables), MAT, FIG (MATLAB files), DOCX, PDF, PPTX, TXT (documents), ASC, NET, SCHDOC (schematic files), GDS, LOG, RAW (EDA outputs), PCBDOC, PRJPCB, GERBER, NC DRILL FILE (PCB projects), AVI, MP4, JPEG, PNG, GIF (Media files), PY, CPP, M (C, C++, python codes, MATLAB).
Volume	Expected size of the dataset
Dissemination level	PR: private, CO: confidential within a specified audience, PU: public
Method of dissemination	How the data are disseminated to the audience and the relevant stakeholders
Beneficiary /communication	To whom the data may be useful

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Datasets Description

Dataset ref code	DOC_Project
Dataset Name	Project data documentation
Dataset Description	Collection of financial and administrative data, information, and periodic reports
Purpose	Support data that document the administrative aspects of the project
Type	Textual documentation
Format	XLSX, DOCX, PDF, PPTX, txt
Volume	Expected Size: MB
Dissemination level	PR, CO, PU
Method of dissemination	Data cannot be shared without permission
Beneficiary/ Communication	Typically, confidential to the European Commission and eventual involved third parties

Dataset ref code	DOC_Report
Dataset Name	Reports, dissemination, and communication documentation
Dataset Description	Reports, deliverables, presentations, publications, and communications, including the project website and social media
Purpose	Support data that describe and document the project developments
Type	Textual and visual documentation
Format	XLSX, DOCX, PDF, PPTX, txt, AVI, MP4, JPEG, PNG, GIF
Volume	Expected Size: GB
Dissemination level	PU, CO
Method of dissemination	Part of the data could be accessed by the technological transfer office of the hosting institute to patenting innovative solutions
Beneficiary/ Communication	Typically, public, or where required confidential to the eventual third parties

Dataset ref code	DATA_RawExp
Dataset Name	Raw experimental data
Dataset Description	Research data from experiments that may or may not be further processed
Purpose	Experimental data used to create models and prove concepts
Type	Electrical, thermal, and mechanical measurements and characterization output
Format	XLSX, CSV, MAT, FIG
Volume	Expected Size: GB
Dissemination level	PR, CO, PU
Method of dissemination	Data cannot be shared without permission
Beneficiary/ Communication	Typically, confidential to the provider, open access where possible and desirable. May be private to a single partner in some cases

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Dataset ref code	DATA_Design
Dataset Name	Design data
Dataset Description	Software, hardware, system, and network designs with related documentation, including scripts, schematics, and netlists
Purpose	Definition of the simulation models
Type	Codes, SPICE schematics, and PCB-related files
Format	PDF, LOG, ASC, NET, SCHDOC, PCBDOC, PRJPCB, GERBER, NC DRILL FILE, PY, CPP, M
Volume	Expected Size: MB
Dissemination level	CO, PU
Method of dissemination	Data can partially be shared as supplementary materials for publications, and part of the data could be accessed by the technological transfer office of the hosting institute to patenting innovative solutions or shared with manufacturing partners.
Beneficiary/Communication	Can be public without revealing partner-related private details

Dataset ref code	DATA_Results
Dataset Name	Processed research data and simulation results
Dataset Description	Processed and analysed results based on raw research data and simulation models, including reports, outcomes, and critical findings. It may include statistical analysis and analytical studies
Purpose	Generate synthetic data based on models that simulate real hardware
Type	Simulations output and elaborated data
Format	XLSX, CSV, MAT, FIG
Volume	Expected Size: GB
Dissemination level	CO, PU
Method of dissemination	Data can partially be shared as materials for publications
Beneficiary/Communication	Can be public without revealing partner-related private details

Dataset ref code	DATA_Multiply
Dataset Name	Multiphysics simulations data
Dataset Description	Products of multiphysics simulation tools
Purpose	Generate files for design and validation of IC and PCB
Type	EDA output
Format	GDS, RAW
Volume	Expected Size: MB
Dissemination level	CO
Method of dissemination	Data cannot be shared
Beneficiary/Communication	Confidential to the provider of the technology

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE

File name description

For published articles, a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) identifying uniquely and permanently the publications, will be assigned by the corresponding journal. For the datasets, a DOI will be assigned by the hosting institution repository. The Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI) repository allows to include metadata descriptors and ensures the long-term preservation of data and metadata.

Each dataset is stored with a name adhering to the following scheme:

SHANNON__Time-stamp__Dataset-type__<Title>

and the name of each file within the DS is chosen according to the following scheme:

Time-stamp__Dataset-type__<Title>__Ver.extension

In these descriptors, we will adopt the following general formats:

- 1) "Dataset-type" is chosen in the set
{DOC_Project, DOC_Report, DATA_RawExp, DATA_Design, DATA_Results, DATA_Multiply}
- 2) <Title> Short description of document (like "Dataset name", for datasets)
- 3) <Timestamp> Date of creation in "yyyymmdd" format
- 4) <Version> Version identifier in progressive order, e.g., 'v1'

Examples of file name

The dataset directory

SHANNON__20230313__DATA_RawExp__Resistance_VPCM_400mV_T150C

will contain all the data/image related to the acquisitions collected on 13 March 2023 regarding the virgin PCM read at 0.4V at 150°C.

The contained data file

20230313__DATA_RawExp__Resistance_VPCM_400mV_T150C_100cells__v1.csv

is a csv file containing the first version of measured data regarding the resistance of 100 virgin PCM cells read at 0.4V at 150°C.

Metadata standard

Metadata will be tagged in XML, fulfilling the requirements of the DataCite and DublinCore metadata schemas/standards. The codebook will contain information on study design, sampling methodology, fieldwork, variable-level detail, and all information necessary for a secondary analyst to use the data accurately and effectively.

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It will be responsibility of:

- each researcher to annotate data with metadata,
- the Principal Investigator to check periodically with all participants to assure data is being properly processed, documented, and stored.

2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

Open Access policy

All SHANNON data sets to be generated will be evaluated with respect to their suitability for open access if it is desirable and not conflicting with IPR. Any dissemination data linked to exploitable results will not be put into the open domain if they compromise its patenting prospects or have inadequate protection. These restrictions will be released as soon as the IPR have been granted. Where such evaluation is positive, data sets will be made available online via research data sharing platforms, with Zenodo identified as the primary option. In addition to the standard metadata, Zenodo includes assignment of a DOI, sophisticated versioning and licensing/access control. In the context of SHANNON, also Github will be used for source codes, but the primary platform will be Zenodo due to its profound advantages regarding versioning and DOI support.

Categories of outputs that SHANNON will give Open Access (free of charge) include:

- Scientific publications
- Research data (Key datasets accompanying publications as supplementary information, that are needed to validate the results)
- Source codes (Physical and/or design models)
- Other research data that may be of interest to scientists, to regulatory bodies and/or to industry

Dissemination and outreach material will be openly available via the SHANNON website and IRIS.

All publications arising from the activities of this project will be deposited in thematic repositories (arXiv, IRIS) and will be published according to gold model of publishing either in open access journals or through open access mode in subscription-based journals. Where this is not possible for any reason, we will use the green model, basing on the SHANNON website and on the IRIS repository (<https://re.public.polimi.it/>).

Finally, the main project outcomes and research results contained in the project deliverables with dissemination level 'public' will be archived by the European Commission via the participant portal and associated systems.

Strategies to limit restrictions

To overcome the problems related to making results openly accessible relating to technical details that cannot be shared, due for example to potential partnerships with third parties, the following strategies will be applied in the limit of respecting the agreements and IPR:

- anonymising or aggregating data
- agreeing a limited embargo period

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

Methods for accessing the data

A README.txt file will be provided in each repository to describe in detail the used software and all the relevant metadata and information regarding the production of data and source codes.

3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

To make data exchange possible standard formats, vocabularies, and document structures will be applied. To ensure interoperability and reusability of the research data, SHANNON has defined several dataset-dependent metadata and descriptive elements to be included for the respective datasets. These will aid interoperability and, combined with the use of research best practices for data generation and high-fidelity scientific results, will ensure data sets generated within SHANNON contain all required information for exploitation by third party researchers.

Metadata will form a subset of data documentation that will explain the purpose, origin, description, time reference, creator, access conditions and terms of use of a data collection. The metadata that would best describe the data depends on the nature of the data. For research data generated in project SHANNON, it is difficult to establish global criteria for all data, since the nature of the initially considered datasets will be different, so that the metadata will be based on a generalized metadata schema as the one used in Zenodo, which includes elements such as:

- **Title:** free text
- **Creator:** Last name, first name
- **Affiliation**
- **Date**
- **Subject:** Choice of keywords and classifications
- **Description:** Text explaining the content of the data set and other contextual information needed for the correct interpretation of the data,
- **Format:** Details of the file format,
- **Resource Type:** data set, image, audio, etc.,
- **Identifier:** DOI
- **Access rights:** closed access, embargoed access, restricted access, open access.

Additionally, a README.txt file could be used as an established way of accounting for all the files and folders comprising the project and explaining how all the files that make up the data set relate to each other, what format they are in or whether files are intended to replace other files.

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4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE

Data retention

Research data made publicly available will be deposited on online sharing and depositing platforms, where storage duration and availability are governed by the service description of the respective platform. In particular, Zenodo has been identified as the default sharing platform for any data sets made publicly available and guarantees storage for at least 20 years, which for the majority of the research data sets generated in SHANNON is considered more than sufficient. The POLIMI repository (IRIS) allows to include metadata descriptors and ensures the long-term preservation of data and metadata too (a copy of the data is automatically deposited at the Data Archiving and Networked Services).

This project could be carried out in collaboration with an industrial partner. In this case, the intellectual property rights will be set out in the collaboration agreement, and datasets loaded on the internal repository may be assigned an embargo period suggested by the IP manager.

Licenses

The intellectual property generated from this project will be fully exploited with help from the institutional Technology Transfer Office (TTO). The aim is to patent the final procedure and then publish the work in a research journal and to publish the supporting data, if possible, under an open Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license. In particular, the CC BY 4.0 license allows to share-copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format, adapt-remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially, under the following terms:

- the user must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, indicate if changes were made and specify that the licensor does not endorse the additional use.
- the user may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Alternatively, the PI can further limit access to the uploaded data by choosing alternative CC licenses, such as the CC BY NC 3.0 license. In this case:

- the user must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, indicate if changes were made and specify that the licensor does not endorse the additional use.
- the user may not use the material for commercial purposes.
- the user may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Data quality assurance

Quality control of data will be guaranteed through the entire lifetime of the SHANNON project, at all the different stages. Data collection will be carried out with the support of experts in the relevant domains, with statistical analysis and observations based on multiple measurements. The data processing will be conducted using standard, reliable and accurate approaches, ensuring all the naming convention to minimize the occurrence probability of human mistakes, typical of work activity carried out by multiple individuals. Finally, outcomes will be checked in terms of accuracy, plausibility, and completeness to properly evaluate the sustainability of the results.

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5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES and DATA SECURITY

Estimated cost for making the data FAIR

The estimated cost of the article processing charges is in average 2.500€ per publication. Considering an estimate of 3 publications within the 18 months of the project life, the total cost of making the data openly accessible for the SHANNON project is about 7.500 €. These estimates are for the open access gold publishing model, which will be preferred to the open access green model. All project-related data will be stored in open access platforms, and therefore free of charge.

Backup and recovery

Any member of the SHANNON team can upload content in the Github/Zenodo repository. The content will be approved by the PI of SHANNON and the IP Manager. All approved items cannot be deleted. New versions of the content can be uploaded together with previous versions to minimize data loss risks. All versions will be simultaneously available.

Value of long-term preservation

Publications of project's research data on the internal repository ensures long-term preservation policies, since a copy of data and metadata will be safely backed up in POLIMI internal Network Attached Storage system. The DOIs provided for datasets will always resolve to a web page, where the dataset metadata and files will be available. In this way, research data will be accessible even though internal repository will be shut down in the future.

Data security

POLIMI implements EU Regulation 2016/679 - "General data protection regulation" and is compliant with the provisions of the minimum-security measures to be adopted pursuant to the Agid Circular of 18 April 2017, no. 2/2017, containing "Misure minime di sicurezza ICT per le pubbliche amministrazioni" ("Minimum ICT security measures for public administrations"). The IT security measures in place to protect against malicious intent are the edge Firewall that supports intrusion prevention system (IPS), antivirus software, a vulnerability assessment that defines, identifies, classifies vulnerabilities in computer systems, applications and network infrastructures, the identity management.